

RESPOND

Working Papers

Global Migration: Consequences and Responses

Paper 2020/36, January 2020

Refugee Protection United Kingdom Country Report

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Recommended Citation: Foley, J. 2020. Refugee Protection UK- Country Report”, Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (#770564, Horizon2020) Report Series.

Reference: RESPOND D3.1

This research was conducted under the Horizon 2020 project ‘RESPOND Multilevel Governance of Migration and Beyond’ (770564). The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author. The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

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Horizon 2020
RESPOND: Multilevel Governance
of Migration and Beyond (770564)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

About the Report

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND will study migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP3, which focuses specifically on asylum procedures and refugee protection.

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List of Abbreviations

AIU	Asylum Intake Unit
APPG	All Party Parliamentary Group
BME	Black and Minority Ethnic
CEAS	Common European Asylum System
CEDAW	Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination Against Women
DFT	Detained Fast Track
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EU	European Union
EURODAC	European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database
FGM	Female Genital Mutilation
UK	United Kingdom
UNHCR	The United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VCRS	Vulnerable Children's Resettlement Scheme
VPRS	Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Scheme

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Umut Korkut, Pinar Aksu, Lena Karamindou, Ela Gokalp Aras and Electra Petracou.

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Executive Summary/Abstract

This report investigates how the UK interprets, narrates and implements its obligations towards international protection for refugees and others that are at significant risk of serious human rights violations and persecution, with an emphasis on the impact of recent migration movements. It explores how the UK applies international protection instruments, particularly the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees/the 1967 Protocol relating to the Status of Refugees and Common European Asylum System (CEAS) directives, and examines the political and policy conflicts that have resulted, most notably with the 2016 “Brexit” referendum on UK membership of the European Union (EU). Highlighting the gaps between policy and the experience of the asylum regime in practice, the report considers the beliefs, coping strategies and perceptions of those who go through the asylum system. It also links experiences and practices to surrounding political narratives, noting how actors in different parts of the asylum system internalise and/or resist the asylum system’s rationalisations.

Protection obligations should be broadly interpreted to include the right to housing, to secure income and employment, to healthcare and to various other social services. These issues (particularly destitution) emerged as significant issues during this research, but, to avoid repetition, they are covered in the forthcoming RESPOND work package 4 report. The same applies to the experience of racism and discrimination in public services and from the public. Equally, the field of protection often branches into areas related to migration control, with many regulations presenting a complex balance between these functions. This has been notable in some recent EU regulations such as Dublin, EURODAC and the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex), but also in efforts to offshore protection to third countries with aid agreements, a recurring feature of both British and European approaches (Gutheil et al., 2018). These matters, considered in WP2, significantly overlap with themes in this report: a crucial impediment to claiming international protection is the difficulty of gaining access to the UK in the first place and the impossibility of starting an asylum from elsewhere (Karamanidou, 2019).

This report’s conclusions are necessarily limited by the uncertainties surrounding the United Kingdom’s future relationship with the EU. As of 2019, the outcome of the “Brexit” process remains unclear. In the concluding sections, the working assumption is that the UK will leave the EU, as is the policy of the current UK Government (e.g. Cutts et al., 2019). However, many proposals will apply regardless of the outcome, as research suggests that the technical policy impact of “Brexit” on the asylum system will be more limited than politicised narratives might suggest (Gutheil et al., 2018).

Key findings in the report include:

- Predating “Brexit”, the UK had the power to optionally opt-out of CEAS directives. It signed up to the first round of directives related to international protection (the Qualification and Procedures directives being particularly relevant to this report), but did not transpose the second round.
- RESPOND’s stakeholder interviews stated, as also emphasised in academic literature and acknowledged in parliamentary reports, a “culture of disbelief” among case workers and others involved in the UK asylum system.
- A significant proportion of those who apply for asylum in the UK face initial rejection, but a sizeable majority appeal and a quarter of those receive their status. Therefore, the tribunal courts play a large role in ensuring the UK adheres to its protection objections, including the core 1951 Convention principle of *non-refoulement*.
- The UK’s narratives of protection present an evolving combination of “humanitarianism” (often linked to the British liberal tradition) with immigration control agendas centred on “bogus” claimants. This means there is a stigma attached to

labels of refugee and (particularly) asylum seeker. The interviews showed evidence of the way actors have internalised these narratives whether as a form of resistance or as a survival strategy.

- The concept of “vulnerability” (including gendered vulnerability) has played a central role in legitimising the UK approach to international protection. However, this priority should be regarded against a backdrop of established institutional barriers to groups such as women and LGBTQ* claimants. Moreover, cuts to welfare and services, added to the “culture of disbelief” among immigration workers, continue to affect the groups targeted as vulnerable.

Introduction

This RESPOND work package explores the impact of recent migration movements on the system of international protection for refugees and others at risk of serious human rights violations and persecution, looking to track changes in the EU, its member states, and third countries significantly affected by recent migration movements, such as Lebanon and Iraq. International protection is officially defined as “all activities aimed at obtaining full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and spirit of the relevant bodies of law, namely human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law” (UNHCR, 2011, p.7). The modern approach to protection emerged with the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, but the scope has broadened in recent decades as many of those fleeing serious harm in a post-colonial context do not fit the official Convention definition of refugee status (Chimni, 2009; Feller, 2001; Williams, 2008).

Dimensions of protection here include access to the asylum system, time-limits for the duration of the application, access to legal assistance, support for vulnerable groups, and the accessibility of the appeals procedure. In this research, a particular focus is the gap between official policies and their implementation in practice by a variety of local, national, and supranational actors. The work package draws on interviews with actors involved at three levels – micro (asylum seekers/refugees), macro (government policymakers) and meso (intermediary groups or representatives) – involved within the protection system. It also draws on an analysis of legal and policy documents and political speeches. It presents conclusions based on these findings, qualified by the uncertainty surrounding the UK’s referendum decision to leave the EU.

The United Kingdom’s approach to international protection reflects the complexities of its geopolitical history, especially its colonial and imperial heritage, and its complex relationship with the EU (Karamanidou, 2019, p.9). In the nineteenth century, Britain operated a liberal, *laissez faire* immigration regime, and significant national pride was associated with offering sanctuary to those seeking refuge from authoritarian European regimes (Price, 2009). The UK efforts to curb migration escalated in the early twentieth century, but the emerging Cold War brought with it an officially tolerant attitude to (European) asylum issues, and the UK was thus a signatory to the Universal Declaration on Human Rights and one of the states to help draft the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol (Webber, 2012, p.19). However, the post-Cold War and post-colonial context meant that the UK framed asylum issues increasingly within a sovereignty and migration control perspective. On at least two occasions since the 1990s, Conservative Party leaders or senior ministers have even proposed withdrawing from the 1951 Convention in an effort to control migration (Webber, 2012, p.23; Wintour, 2005). Although these policies never materialised, a racialized migration control perspective on the asylum system has largely characterised the policy programme of both the Conservative and the Labour Party (Maughan, 2010; Mulvey, 2011). The asylum system has been stigmatised by efforts to associate it with the alleged criminality of the global south (Huysmans and Buonfino, 2008; Malloch and Stanley, 2005). Nonetheless, political leaders of both parties continue to emphasise the UK’s leading role in human rights and international protection, explicitly linking this to the nation’s history and liberal traditions.

The UK has adapted its system to some of the instruments of the CEAS, which aimed to define minimum EU-wide standards for asylum qualification, reception and procedures. However, since the UK has the right to opt-out of its provisions, they have been implemented in a piecemeal fashion: the UK thus implemented the first round of CEAS directives, but not the second round, citing concerns over new directives on giving asylum seekers’ right to work after six (later amended to nine) months of a non-decision, restrictions on asylum detention, and limits to fast-track procedures (Migration Observatory, 2014, p.4). UK Governments also disagreed with the EU over efforts to establish “quota” systems to relocate and resettle refugees (e.g. Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.19). Nonetheless, the House of

Lords has established that the first round of CEAS directives continues to apply, despite initial uncertainty over whether they could be invalidated by the UK's decision to opt-out of later rounds (Migration Observatory, 2014, p.4).

To avoid confusion, we refer to Directive 2005/85/EC as the "Procedures Directive" unless otherwise specified. Similarly, Directive 2004/83/EC is referred here as the "Qualification Directive".

In the context of the Syrian Civil War, growing external migration to the European Union exposed tensions in UK politics. The politicisation of the asylum system was a factor in the "Brexit" referendum, which led to a decision to leave the European Union. The official Leave campaign's slogan of "take back control" referred to many elements of national sovereignty, but the context of real or imagined increasing migration was widely noted (Gamble, 2018; Virdee and McGeever, 2018). The unofficial "Leave.EU",¹ led by the populist right spokesman Nigel Farage, released a billboard poster with the slogan "Breaking Point: The EU is Failing Us All", picturing a large queue of (seemingly) non-White people crossing borders. This was evidently an attempt to politicise specifically extra-EU migration and thus the asylum system rather than the more obviously referendum-related theme of internal EU migration. However, it would be misleading to present the rhetoric of Brexit as a qualitative break from established UK narratives: there are significant points of continuity, with both major UK parties have politicised "bogus" asylum seekers since the 1990s. Nonetheless, as the conclusion will suggest, the Brexit outcome has left considerable contradictions in how the UK will continue to manage its international protection obligations alongside its immigration control agenda.

¹ A campaign, associated with the populist right, which sought unsuccessfully to become the official Leave campaign in the UK's European Union referendum. It continued as an unofficial body and was widely credited with associating the campaign with immigration.

Methodology and Sources

The section on political narratives emerged from a qualitative content analysis of speeches and statements by two Prime Ministers/Home Secretaries since 2011, specifically Theresa May and David Cameron. These were drawn from the UK Government's website using the keywords "asylum", "refugee" and "Syria", and 31 were specifically selected for analysis based on their relevance for themes of international protection. Initially coding structures were taken from academic literature and from previous RESPOND UK and comparative reports. Themes were also identified in an inductive manner and reviewed on an iterative basis. Analysis was conducted with NVivo qualitative data analysis software. The legal framework draws from a literature review plus prior work carried out by the RESPOND team at the University of Cambridge as part of work package 1 (Hirst and Atto, 2018).

Data for the practices and experiences section was largely drawn from two sets of semi-structured interviews. The first set of 16 meso-level interviews focused on the experiences of stakeholders from public and local authorities and third sector groups such as the Asylum Seeker Housing Project, local community groups, and branches of established NGOs like the Red Cross, recruited through direct contact or snowballing techniques. A second set of 15 micro-level interviews was conducted with refugees and asylum seekers in Cambridge and Glasgow. The interviews were coded with NVivo following RESPOND's common coding structure.

The micro-level sample provided a balanced mixture of ethnicities. In total, three respondents originated in Iran; five from Syria; four from Iraq; two from Pakistan; and one from Afghanistan. The sample was limited by the small number of women respondents (three) and the absence of LGBTQ* and disabled respondents. Further details are listed in Annex 5. Respondents were asked a range of questions relating to their reception conditions, with topics including their housing situation, any periods of detention, their health (including mental health) and access to services.

Background of the National Legal and Institutional Framework

Important Developments since 2011

The UK's international protection framework has experienced both practical and ideological pressures since 2011 with the growth of external migration, domestic political conflict, and legal challenges.

As with most European states, the outcomes of the Syrian Civil War proved the major test of the established UK system. The Government's initial response was to offer external humanitarian relief and propose geopolitical interventions rather than committing to resettlement programmes that threatened to undermine radical targets to reduce net migration. However, first in 2014, and to a significantly greater extent in 2015, the government established the Syrian Vulnerable Person Resettlement Scheme (VPRS) as a pathway for Syrians to resettle in the UK (McGuinness, 2017, p.3; Home Office, 2018c). Later, the Vulnerable Children's Resettlement Scheme (VCRS) was introduced specifically for the resettlement of refugee children: in April 2016 the Government committed to resettle 3,000 "at risk" children from the Middle East and North Africa, not limited to Syria, by 2020 (Home Office, 2018c, p.5; APPG Refugees, 2017, p.11). The so-called "Dubs amendment" to the Immigration Act 2016 also committed the UK to relocate unaccompanied children from Europe to the UK with priority given to those at risk of abuse and exploitation (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.56). Nonetheless, the UK has resisted Europe-wide relocation programmes, and has continued to take the view that aid to neighbouring countries is "preferable to encouraging Syrian refugees to make dangerous journeys to Europe" (McGuinness, 2017, p.4).

The policies of Conservative governments (initially in coalition with the Liberal Democrats) also had wider implications for the protection system. Since 2010, consecutive Home Office administrations have committed to creating a "hostile environment" (later renamed "compliant environment") for migration through restrictions on welfare and public services (Karamanidou, 2019, pp.11–12). This visibly impacted, not only on asylum seekers occupying the liminal space between protected refugee status and the stigmatised role of "irregular" and "economic migrants", but even on longstanding black and minority ethnic communities. The "Windrush Scandal", when 83 people were wrongly deported from the UK including many who had lived in the UK prior to 1973, was the most publicised illustration of how the "hostile environment" extended well beyond its immediate targets (Wardle and Obermuller, 2019).

The coalition's central economic policy commitment to austerity also impacted on refugees and asylum seekers with growing evidence of those seeking protection being pushed into destitution (e.g. Refugee Action, 2017). A key example related to international protection has been the reduced availability of appropriate legal aid services in parts of Britain with the emergence of "legal deserts" and significant geographical cleavages in terms of access to justice (Burridge and Gill, 2017). However, if "protection" is interpreted in its broader sense, the impact of austerity extends into many areas of refugee experience, a matter that will be explored in greater depth in Work Package 4.

One notable exception to the draconian trend in recent UK asylum legislation was the suspension of the Detained Fast Track (DFT) system in July 2015 (Firth and Clayton, 2018, p.26; Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.44). DFT involved detaining with a view to deporting in cases where the Home Office considered that the case could be decided quickly, but it was heavily criticised, including by Parliamentary committees (APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015). At its height, DFT meant one in four asylum seekers were detained through the course of their claim, with rejection rates for those claims being 99 percent (Detention Action, 2017). Officially, the programme was "temporarily suspended" (Home Office, 2015b,

p.1). A new asylum processing system for those already in detention, known as Detained Asylum Casework, has been installed (Home Office, 2019b), and there have been (so far unsuccessful) legal challenges to this new system based on its similarity to DFT (Electronic Immigration Network, 2016).

Finally, the policy environment surrounding protection has been marked, rhetorically at least, by the mood of uncertainty surrounding “Brexit”, the United Kingdom’s declared intention to leave the European Union. The UK referendum in 2016 was widely interpreted as a mandate to “take back control” of immigration (Gamble, 2018; Virdee and McGeever, 2018). This has caused alarm among migrants and black and minority ethnic communities as well as refugees. Firm conclusions are impossible at this stage, given the uncertainty surrounding the implementation of the referendum (Hirst and Atto, 2018, pp.7–8), but potential implications will be considered in the concluding chapter.

National legal and institutional framework regarding “asylum procedure and refugee protection”

The UK’s asylum procedure and refugee protection system is founded on the 1951 Refugee Convention and the 1967 Protocol, which sets out the broad international standards for defining refugees and states’ responsibilities towards them based on the core principle of *non-refoulement* (e.g. UNHCR, 2017, p.17). Subsequently, interpretation of the Convention has been shaped by the Common European Asylum System (CEAS). The UK’s participation in this system’s instruments is optional, and, since 2013, the UK has opted-out of future participation in expanding the system into its second phase (Migration Observatory, 2014, p.2). However, Britain did opt in to the first phase of CEAS including the directives imposing minimum standards for asylum procedures and qualification policy on member states. The UK transposed those regulations into law with The Refugee or Person in Need of International Protection (Qualification) Regulations 2006 and Part 11 of the Immigration Rules (Home Office, 2015a, p.6). In the UK, refugee status is thus determined by applying Article 1A(2) of the Refugee Convention, interpreted according to the EU’s Qualification Directive (Firth and Clayton, 2018, p.439). Additionally, the system has been shaped by the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which was incorporated into UK law as the Human Rights Act 1998. Since the Convention’s provisions largely protect those who are given refugee status, rather than those who apply for it, the Human Rights Act has been important in safeguarding international protection for those occupying the liminal asylum seeker status (Justice, 2008).

CEAS introduced requirements for subsidiary protection provisions for those people that fail to meet the criteria of refugee as defined in the Convention (Home Office, 2017). The rules governing this were transposed into UK law with the Qualification Directive, and the category of “Humanitarian Protection” thus replaced the earlier policy of Exceptional Leave to Remain (Home Office, 2017, p.6). In practice, the process governing Humanitarian Protection follows largely the same path as the mainstream asylum procedure. The EU Procedures Directive requires that any application for international protection should be considered an asylum claim even if the applicant does not claim to be a Convention defined refugee (Home Office, 2017, p.9). Additionally, people can apply to remain in the UK with a human rights claim under the ECHR. Technically, this means that returning them to their country of origin would breach the Convention usually on the grounds of Article 3 (prohibition on torture and inhuman or degrading treatment) or Article 8 (right to respect for family life and private life) (Home Affairs Committee, 2013, p.9). These claims can form part of an asylum claim but can also be made separately from it, and form a layer of additional protection through the appeals system (Right to Remain, 2018, pp.78–81).

Lastly, the UK has programmes for resettling people who have been granted refugee status while living in another country. While the UK has no large-scale, permanent

resettlement programmes (Sturge, 2019, p.5), it has introduced specific resettlement policies in response to major humanitarian issues such as the Syrian Civil War (McGuinness, 2017). Recipients of the resettlement programmes are a minority of refugees living in the UK. However, as demonstrated in the narratives section, these schemes have played a notable role in discourses surrounding humanitarianism and immigration control.

Legislation and Immigration Rules

While the UK system is based on international provisions, it has been shaped in practice by primary and secondary legislation. Primary legislation is set out in a series of Acts, all originating from the Immigration Act 1971. A summary of Key Acts is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Recent UK Legislation Relating to International Protection

Act	Implications
Asylum and Immigration Appeals Act 1993	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Established the category of an asylum claim “without foundation”, curtailing appeal rights
Asylum and Immigration Act 1996	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expanded definition of ingenuine claims to include a specified list of safe countries, New offences for facilitating unauthorised entry, Employers obliged to check immigration status of employees.
Immigration and Asylum Act 1999	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Removed asylum seekers from mainstream benefits system, Ended support for “failed” asylum seekers with no dependents, Dispersal of asylum seekers around the UK, Restrictions on appeal rights, Expansion of system of fines for transporting undocumented passengers.
Nationality Immigration and Asylum Act 2002	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ingenuine asylum seekers relabelled “clearly unfounded” and now decided on the basis of a safe country list. Asylum seekers failing to quickly lodge claims could be deprived of housing and subsistence support.
Immigration, Asylum and Nationality Act 2006	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Greater enforcement powers e.g. fining employers over violations such as employing people without the right to work.
UK Borders Act 2007	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Removed appeal rights for those facing deportation. Gave immigration officers expanded powers of detention. Introduced biometric identification.
Immigration Act 2014	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Associated with the “hostile environment”. Various restrictions targeting those who provide services for those deemed illegal immigrants, e.g. preventing landlords renting houses to people without legal status.
Immigration Act 2016	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further measures targeting unauthorised migrants. Employing or renting accommodation to those without permission to work or rent is now a criminal offence. Immigrants without permission to be in the UK can have bank accounts frozen, driver’s license confiscated. Allows for the withdrawal of support from refused asylum seeking families.

Source: Adapted from Hirst, C., Atto, N., 2018. United Kingdom - Country Report: Legacy & Policy Framework of Migration Governance. RESPOND Working Papers, Cambridge, pp. 35-7.

As observed in the WP1 UK RESPOND report, “the general trend since 1971 has been ever greater immigration restrictions – along the themes of eroded appeal rights, expanding the surveillance apparatus, limiting social benefits, and depriving asylum seekers of a thorough review of their claim if they are deemed to be ingenuine at the outset” (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.35). Nonetheless, the trend has not been unidirectional. The right to appeal was established in the Asylum and Immigration Appeals Act 1993. The Human Rights Act 1998 gave new safeguards and protections to all immigrants and the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999 established the right to make immigration appeals on human rights grounds (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.37). There have also been new regulations specifically targeting “vulnerable” grounds such as women, children and victims of trafficking (Home Office, 2018b), including the Modern Slavery Act 2015 (Home Office, 2019d), although researchers have suggested that the draconian conditions imposed in the UK asylum system continues to offer an environment for these forms of exploitation to continue (e.g. Kidd, Faulkner and Arocha, 2019).

In UK Law, the Immigration Act 1971 empowers the Secretary of State to make “Immigration Rules” governing when a person is permitted to stay in the UK (Hirst and Atto, 2018, pp.37–8). This secondary legislation forms a major part of the UK system, and usually receive little scrutiny (House of Commons Home Affairs Committee, 2018, p.16). New rules are presented before the Parliament for 40 days after which they become law. In practice, Immigration Rules are rarely debated, and they have been rejected only a handful of times (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.16; Hirst and Atto, 2018, pp.37–8). The Home Office also issues guidance for caseworkers involved in determining status (Home Office, 2019a, 2015a). This deals with practical issues of applying the law, conducting interviews, and assessing the credibility of the case, often on the basis of “country of origin” information giving an explanation of the social and political circumstances in the applicant’s nation.

Application Procedures

Applicants can apply for asylum when they arrive at a UK border, but this only occurs in a minority of cases. Alternatively, if applying post-arrival, they must attend at the Asylum Intake Unit² in Croydon, London, or, if they are detained, they may apply at the detention centre (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.15). In exceptional cases, these conditions can be waived on the grounds of destitution or vulnerability, but this happens in a small minority of cases (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.18; Hutton, Simic and Blitz, 2017, p.8).

The first step is a *screening interview* with an immigration officer, where the asylum claim is registered and the officer decides if they will be detained or admitted temporarily. During this process, biometric data is taken, alongside information about health, family circumstances, details of route of travel, and their broad case for asylum (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.15; Home Office, 2018a). Unaccompanied children are directed to a specially trained decision maker, otherwise the outcome of the screening interview determines which procedure the applicant will follow namely regular procedure (general casework), accelerated procedure, and the safe third country procedure (see also Right to Remain, 2018, pp.58–60).

With the regular procedure, the applicant attends a further asylum interview with a caseworker to assess the evidence of their claim. Until 2019, the vast majority of “straightforward” cases through the standard procedure were meant to be resolved within six months; however, the Home Office officially abandoned this target, having come nowhere

² Previously named the Asylum Screening Unit.

near to meeting it (Allison and Taylor, 2019). Successful applicants can be granted refugee status, humanitarian protection, or discretionary leave to remain (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.43). Alternatively, if their claim is rejected, they have a right of appeal, and the right to remain in the UK while the appeal is heard.

Accelerated procedure applies if a case is judged as “clearly unfounded” (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.44). Although this judgement may be based on individual circumstances, the most common reason is that the applicant comes from a country that has been designated in law as “safe” (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.15). In 2018, a total of 1,285 cases were deemed clearly unfounded, roughly 4 percent of total asylum claims (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.39). The consequence of this status is that appeals are “non-suspensive”, i.e., the applicant has no right to appeal from within the UK and the appeal process cannot be used as grounds to stop deportation. Detained Fast Track (DFT), a second route for accelerated decision making, was suspended in 2015 following legal challenges (see above).

The final route is the third country procedure (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.44; Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.15). During the screening interview, the officer may conclude that the applicant has passed through a safe third country on their way to the UK. In these circumstances, their case is transferred to the Home Office’s Third Country Unit. They may be detained subject to transfer to another EU country under the Dublin Regulation or to another country they have passed through *en route*. As with “clearly unfounded” cases, there is no right to appeal within the system and the only recourse is judicial review.

The appeals process is central to the UK system since a large number of cases are rejected erroneously at the Home Office stage (Burrige and Gill, 2017, p.25). Claimants initially appeal to the First Tier Tribunal (Immigration and Asylum Chamber), part of the Ministry of Justice’s unified tribunal structure (Firth and Clayton, 2018, p.245). The tribunals are adversarial (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.16) and the Home Office is represented by a presenting officer. Appeals on points of law can be made to the Upper Tribunal with permission from either the First Tier or the Upper Tribunal. Points of law could include the First Tier making a mistake on a point of asylum law, failing to follow a binding decision of a higher court, or failing to include important evidence (Firth and Clayton, 2018, pp.245–6).

Those applicants who are rejected through the standard procedure can appeal through the judicial system (Hirst and Atto, 2018, pp.30–2). Historically, the UK has three legal systems: England and Wales; Scotland; and Northern Ireland. However, since asylum issues are reserved to Westminster, all tribunals are administered centrally through the HM Courts and Tribunal Service, which has two tiers: the First-Tier Tribunal and the Upper Tier Tribunal. Appeals against Home Office decisions are heard initially in the First-Tier Tribunal (Immigration and Asylum Chamber). Appeals against First-Tier decisions are referred, with permission, to the Upper Tribunal. If this appeal is also lost, the applicant may have recourse to a higher court: the Court of Appeal in England and Wales, the Court of Appeal in Northern Ireland, and the Court of Session in Scotland (Hirst and Atto, 2018, p.31).

Finally, a notable feature of the UK system is the prevalence of administrative detention. Detention is, officially speaking, a secondary part of the mainstream of the UK asylum system. According to Home Office policy, “Detention must be used sparingly, and for the shortest period necessary” (UK Visas and Immigration, 2019). However, in 2018 a total of 12,637 in immigration detention had sought asylum at some point, which amounts to roughly half (51%) of all people entering the detention system (Silverman and Griffiths, 2019, p.7). This can last for extended periods of time, since the UK is one of only two EU countries not to ratify the EU Returns Directive 2008/115/EC, which limits detention to six months barring exceptional circumstances (APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015, p.16).

Key narratives regarding international protection (asylum procedure and refugee protection)

This section builds on an analysis of post-2011 speeches by UK Prime Ministers and Home Secretaries to assess the UK's key narratives surrounding international protection. Many of these themes such as the conflation of asylum with “illegal immigration”, the framework of “immigration control”, and criminalisation are well established in research literature (e.g. Philo, Briant and Donald, 2013, pp.141–53). The analysis suggests that such themes remain integral to the discourses of UK leaders. However, the motivations behind these policies and discourses are also articulated in “humanitarian” terms, and UK leaders suggest that their approach to international protection is more virtuous than comparable systems, particularly those organised on an EU-wide framework. Appeals are made to distinctive British liberal historical traditions, and the UK's recent schemes are built on a critical stance on the established system of refugee protection. However, notably these points tend to build towards proposals that centre on limiting the numbers of protection-seekers, who reach UK borders spontaneously. In sum, recent UK leaders have presented humanitarianism and immigration control as complementary rather than contradictory perspectives.

The humanitarian claims of UK governments are regularly criticised including from within the established political structures (APPG Refugees, 2017; e.g. APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015). Concepts of humanitarianism, generosity and vulnerability serve as a basis for government claim-making, but also for criticising them. Researchers generally note that by international standards the UK takes less than its “share” of international protection obligations, especially given that the main vast majority of refugees are hosted outside of the Global North (e.g. Migration Observatory, 2015; The Guardian, 2017a). Even compared to the EU average, the UK manages a low volume of claims: there are 5 asylum applications for every 10,000 UK residents, compared to the EU average of 14 per 10,000, ranking 17th out of 28 countries (Sturge, 2019, p.3). However, UK governments reject quantitative measures, and instead stress the qualitative measure of “vulnerability” as the correct gauge of a nation's successful accomplishment of its protection obligations. The key puzzle of the UK narrative is how they have not only *balanced* immigration control with “humanitarianism”, but attempted to tie a regime of deterrence with a scheme targeting granting asylum to the “most vulnerable”, thus allowing them to overcome the dichotomy and present their schemes as more virtuous.

Humanitarian Narratives

Analysis of political speeches shows that a formal “humanitarianism” forms part of the discourse of justification for the UK international protection regime. Successive Prime Ministers have emphasised that Britain is a “welcoming” place for those who need international protection. “We are granting asylum to those who need it, consistent with this country's proud tradition of giving help to those who need it most” (May, 2014). This is said to reflect a distinct strain of liberty and respect for the individual in British culture, political institutions and history, a narrative with some historical basis pre-twentieth century (Price, 2009), although less so in contemporary history (for criticism of this narrative, see e.g. Erel, Murji and Nahaboo, 2016; Holmes, 2015). Importantly, the discourse presents asylum as – theoretically speaking – a worthy cause, signifying the virtue of the host country. Nonetheless, these statements rarely appear in unqualified form. The example below highlights a common tactic of balancing an assertion of humanitarianism with a qualification focusing on the unfair “burdens” imposed on Britain:

Britain will always be open to those who are seeking asylum from persecution.
That says something very important about the kind of country we are and we

should be proud of that too. But excessive immigration brings pressures, real pressures on our communities up and down the country. Pressures on schools, housing and healthcare and social pressures too (Cameron, 2013).

The humanitarian narrative can serve dual purposes. In the above analysis, which draws from Conservative government speeches, it serves as a *rationalisation* for practices of control: asserting British leadership on the humanitarian front functions to legitimise a strong policing approach, a counterweight to policy proposals focused on deterrence, and combating perceived abuses. However, where NGOs, lawyers and opposition politicians appeal to British humanitarian traditions or to other humanitarian value systems, these discourses form the basis of critical oversight of government policies, and may under certain circumstances shift policy away from immigration control.

These nuances reflect the varying functions of asylum in the imaginary of British geopolitics. The narrative of refuge initially served to rationalise liberal-democratic and Cold War opposition to totalitarian regimes, but since the 1990s, in a post-Cold War context, the new asylum seekers from the global south have increasingly been framed as a problem requiring containment (Chimni, 1998; Erel, Murji and Nahaboo, 2016). The outcomes of the Syrian Civil War exposed new tensions in this balance between humanitarianism and deterrence. Thus, a Parliamentary Report specifically notes that the UK's series of policy responses, which included the VPRS, was a consequence of the humanitarian reaction to pictures of the drowned asylum seeker Alan Kurdi (APPG Refugees, 2017, p.9). After an initially deterrence-focused response, David Cameron's government was forced to issue statements of humanitarian concern: Cameron even argued that "no country has done more than Britain when it comes to help for Syrian refugees" (Prime Minister's Office, 2016). Here, Cameron's assertion of the UK's humanitarian virtue serves to shield his government from criticisms of its record in practice. This reflected a rhetorical shift from earlier efforts to downplay the UK's role in Syria to appease populist sentiment. The claim rests in part on the UK's reframing of humanitarianism on a broader basis, limiting the role of the established asylum system, and instead emphasising aid to conflict-adjacent countries and geopolitical interventions in civil wars.

Vulnerability Narratives

UK Governments have presented recent schemes for resettling the "most vulnerable" refugees – notably the VPRS – as alternatives to the standard asylum system. Resettlement is represented as a distinctive UK approach, and an alternative to relocation within Europe or to admitting greater numbers of applicants into UK borders. "We will not be taking more refugees – we have our programme of resettling people direct from the refugee camps and that stays the same" (Cameron, 2016) has been a trope characterising the resettlement policy. In the UK Government's discourse, their system of resettlement is simultaneously a mechanism of "controlled immigration" and a more altruistic approach than comparable European schemes, which allows political leaders to bridge conflicting narratives of humanitarianism and border control.

These claims rest on the criterion of "vulnerability", which serves as a critical stance on the established international system for managing refugees. They claim that the existing global asylum "system is geared towards helping those most able to access it, and sometimes manipulate it, for their own ends – those who are young enough, fit enough, and have the resources to get to Britain" and as a result, "support is too often denied to the most vulnerable, and those most in need of our help" (May, 2015). The category of the deserving, hand-selected refugee is, in most cases, built on a contrast with the undeserving, spontaneously-arriving asylum seeker.

One effect of the vulnerability discourse has been a two-tier system (APPG Refugees, 2017, p.6) with the resettlement programmes being better resourced and supported.

Moreover, the categories used to measure vulnerability have initiated new labels that reinforce the discourses of “bogusness” and “deterrence”. For example, under Conservative governments, the Home Office has developed a discourse of “imposter children”, i.e., asylum seekers falsely claiming to be children (and thus vulnerable) to gain easier access. The idea of imposter-children, and the age-assessment regime that goes with it, has been said to be “being discursively constructed in order to justify popular and official suspicion of spontaneously arriving child asylum-seekers in favour of resettling refugees from camps abroad” (Silverman, 2016, p.30; see also McLaughlin, 2018; Cemlyn and Nye, 2012).

“Vulnerability”, the apparently neutral and humanitarian category underlying these distinctions, may have other implicit assumptions. Some researchers claim that positioning asylum seekers as vulnerable and thus dependent raises the importance of intermediaries, such as NGOs and public sector professionals, at the expense of the autonomy of the agency of asylum seekers themselves (Crawley, 2011; O’Higgins, 2012; Rainbird, 2011). Equally, the rationalisation of the system as being a defence of women and children positions makes the adult male asylum seeker “less vulnerable” or even “not vulnerable” (Allsopp, 2017; Griffiths, 2015; Wray, 2015). Another effect noted by Yeo is a decisive shift in the framework of protection, as what was framed historically as a “(human) right” is positioned instead as a “gift” rewarded by the state to the most deserving (see also Goodman, Sirriyeh and McMahon, 2017; Goodman and Speer, 2007).

Threat, “Bogusness” and Criminality Narratives

In the 1990s and 2000s, the phrase “asylum seeker” was often preceded by the adjective “bogus”, in a discourse that tended to cut across party lines (Philo, Briant and Donald, 2013, pp.60–2; Lynn and Lea, 2003; Malloch and Stanley, 2005; Maughan, 2010; Mulvey, 2011). The specific phrase “bogus asylum seeker” has been less prominent in the past decade. However, “bogus students” emerged as a recurring theme in the analysis of speeches by David Cameron, and his references to “bogusness” have an established genealogy in one of the most entrenched British political discourses. While this discourse does not directly implicate asylum seekers, it continues to draw on the negative associations established in relation to this group, demonstrating the continued relevance of these narratives for some political actors.

The suggestion of pervasive false claims in the asylum system remains an established theme in political leader discourses. Indeed, beyond “bogusness” and “economic migration”, British leaders will often link asylum to other threats: “there is a huge difference between a young Syrian family fleeing the tyranny of ISIL or Assad, and a student that claims asylum once he has been discovered overstaying his visa or a foreign criminal about to be sent to a prison in his own country” (May, 2015). Alleged “abuses” of the asylum system for “economic” purposes are already subject to draconian measures, but there are long-established narratives in British politics, linking human rights legislation, the asylum system, and other forms of protection to criminality and even terrorism (Bhatia, 2015; Greenslade, 2005; Malloch and Stanley, 2005).

The various threats, economic, security-related and also to national identity, are often bundled together in media narratives (Innes, 2010). Economic threats combine the risk to domestic jobs – heavily exaggerated when linked to asylum, given the absence of the right to work – and the “burden” of asylum seekers on welfare and services. Security threats involve allegations of terrorist infiltration via the system. National identity (and sometimes “European” identity), meanwhile, are said to be threatened by the demographic changes the asylum system involves. Such connections are more explicitly expressed in mass media narratives (Philo, Briant and Donald, 2013) than in political speeches. However, political leaders continue to frame the issues in a connected fashion, mentioning the various aspects

of threat in speeches about the asylum system and not correcting media narratives which give a misleading impression of the scale of the threat.

Immigration Control Narratives

Immigration control and asylum functions have become increasingly interconnected since the 1990s (Chimni, 1998; Webber, 2012). Recently, Conservative government have promised to bring net migration “down radically from hundreds of thousands a year, to just tens of thousands” (Cameron, 2013). As part of this, the central narrative for all Home Office functions relating to immigration has been the “hostile environment” (later renamed “compliant environment”) for individuals, who are in the UK without valid leave as outlined in the Immigration Acts 2014 and 2016 (Karamanidou, 2019, p.11). What has differentiated the “hostile environment” from earlier immigration control narratives – besides the drastic nature of the targets – is that it actively seeks the co-optation of new layers of the public sector in policing the immigration system.

Formally, the hostile environment makes the established distinguish between “deserving” and “undeserving” migrants, a narrative which is embedded and internalised in much of the UK, including among ethnic minority communities (Dhaliwal and Forkert, 2015). This would theoretically exclude legitimate protection seekers and focus instead on “failed” asylum seekers and other “economic migrants”. May thus called for “better distinguishing between economic migrants and refugees, swiftly returning those who have no right to remain and thereby sending out a deterrence message to others thinking of embarking on perilous journeys” (May, 2017). However, even aside from the always questionable nature of these dichotomies, the hostile/compliant environment programme has been notable for its failures to make these distinctions and for its impact even on long-established black and ethnic minority communities.

The “hostile environment” narrative reinforces boundary distinctions between legitimate and illegitimate immigration, and to reinforce stigmatising associations between the latter and criminality/threat. Asylum seekers are, administratively speaking, positioned between the status of “good” refugee and “bad” economic migrant. The analysis of hostile environment narratives suggests that asylum seekers will be increasingly aware of their liminal status and of the stigma attached to it and will be forced to internalise distinctions between “good” and “bad” migrants.

Asylum Procedure and Refugee Protection: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions

This chapter explores the implementation of asylum procedures and refugee protection, focusing on the gap between policy and practice and the conflict between societal narratives and actors' experiences. The themes are drawn from analysis of two sets of interviews conducted during RESPOND fieldwork: one on the experiences of meso-level practitioners involved in securing protection (n=16) and the other with current and former asylum seekers (n=15). In general, the choice of topics reflects the issues that most commonly arose during coding of interviews. However, certain themes directly related to protection – such as health, destitution and experiences of localised racism – will be explored in WP4 to prevent overlap between the two reports. The themes are compared against relevant law and policy documents, most commonly EU Directives and Home Office guidance but also parliamentary reports and other official documents. Where possible, the themes are also linked to the narratives of protection established in the previous chapter for three purposes: to show the conflict between official claims (e.g. of “humanitarianism”) and experience; to demonstrate how narratives (e.g. the “hostile environment”) impact on international protection; and to examine how actors internalise or resist dominant narratives (e.g. of the “good” refugee). Finally, the findings have been triangulated against academic and policy research to demonstrate continuity and gaps in the existing literature.

Experience with Actors: the “Culture of Disbelief”

Researchers have presented the UK procedures for refugee status determination as a “culture of disbelief” (Anderson, 2014; Souter, 2011), acknowledged in a UK Parliamentary committee as “the tendency of those evaluating applications to start from the assumption that the applicant is not telling the truth” (Home Affairs Committee, 2013, p.11). In academic studies, the culture of disbelief has been seen as a “subculture” among immigration officers operating beneath official regulation (Jubany, 2017, 2011). The phenomenon has been increasingly recognised outside of academic research and a Home Affairs Committee (2013) enquiry found that almost a quarter of written submissions made reference to it. Indeed, the culture is recognised enough that the UK Government has issued an official denial of its existence: “The Government does not accept there is a ‘culture of disbelief’, meaning a prejudice on the part of caseworkers” (UK Government, 2013, p.4). Nonetheless, they admitted that

It is of course true...that many if not most asylum claims hinge on credibility, in the sense of whether, often in the absence of independently verifiable evidence, the caseworker believes the facts as presented by the asylum seeker...This can lead to suggestions that the bar is sometimes set too high, or that a different view could have been taken, or that misunderstandings arise in some cases. Some construe this as a culture of disbelief (UK Government, 2013, p.5).

The experiences in previous sections suggest that those that undergo the asylum system are conscious of feeling disbelieved by those they encounter. The theme also emerged strongly during meso-level interviews with agencies that negotiate between asylum seekers and the Home Office system:

It's the hostile environment, but I think it's also shortage of staff and incompetence. I mean, the cuts, the Home Office and the border agency were subjected quite heavy cuts and I think if you are short of staff and under pressure you are likely to be less pleasant and sympathetic than you would be. I think, you know, there is this culture of disbelief and that is intensified by

people feeling overworked and stressed (meso level interview with Maryhill Integration Network).

I've got a family at the moment and their main bone of contention for why they have been refused is that they don't believe she is from the country that she is from and that they think she is from [African country] and she has never even been near [African country]. And she is just so completely undermined mentally you know, with where has this even come from because that is such a surprising answer that's it's just almost like been too bizarre for them to even fathom. She's been like, I don't know the first thing about [African country], you know, why would they think that I am from there (meso level interview with Scottish Green Party councillor).

I think the fundamental issue with the hostile environment is it disbelieves everybody. You are guilty until proven innocent, which is not how justice works (meso level interview with Scottish Green Party councillor).

The interviewee above explains that “the culture of disbelief...is intensified by [Home Office staff] feeling overworked and stressed”. Although denied by the Home Office, the link between caseworker behaviour and a managerial culture of efficiency, targets and cost reductions have been reported. Leaks from inside UK Visas and Immigration have suggested that some workers are incentivised to make negative judgements or to make poor quality decisions. According to informers from the Dublin Cessation Team (previously the Third Country Unit), there are performance targets where staff are given 555 minutes to refuse an asylum application compared to 222 minutes to grant one, incentivising poorly trained and overworked case workers to reject claims to meet targets (Hill, 2019). Previously, a similar whistle-blower from a different part of the Home Office asylum system testified that decisions are a “lottery” because such a high volume of cases must be dealt with every week to clear backlogs (Brewer, 2018).

Yeah, I say to them I have hepatitis, but they say, "No, we don't believe you." When I go to hospital, I have hepatitis. Because they play, the Home Office people is playing to your mind, inside - they will damage you. I see a lot of people, refugees, first they refuse, because they don't understand the language, nobody know how you can live, they're always at home. Then suddenly they are crazy and the mind is not working, then paper is coming (AFM01³, micro-level interview).

Those who had experienced the asylum system usually showed at least some awareness of the surrounding societal narratives that produced disbelief. Their survival strategies varied in this context. Some, particularly those with an intellectual or political activism background, assumed a stance of resistance, qualified by their knowledge that the asylum system offered few outlets for risk-free expressions of conflict. Others responded by internalising the narrative of “good” refugees and “bad” migrants with their complaints centring on how their legitimate claim was being undermined by the instrumentalism of less deserving applicants.

Interview Experiences

Asylum seekers will complete a screening interview to determine their pathway (see Section X) and, under most circumstances (see section on Application Procedures), they will then undergo substantive interviews that form much of the basis of refugee status determination (Home Office, 2019a, 2018a, 2015a). The legal context for this is established

³ See Annex V.

in Articles 12-14 of the Procedures Directive, which are reflected in Part 11 of the UK Immigration Rules. Oral testimony will be judged both for its internal coherence and for its consistency with the externally known facts. It is of crucial importance to the outcome of a case as the Home Office also acknowledges: “the claimant’s testimony is usually the most important evidence, often the only substantive evidence” (Home Office, 2015a, p.8). The proper conduct of interviews is, therefore, among the most crucial components towards ensuring that claims are properly heard.

Thus, the implementation notes for Home Office case worker urges them to “be open and relaxed and non-threatening to do all you can to create an environment in which the claimant feels able to disclose relevant and potentially highly personal and sensitive information” (Home Office, 2019a, p.10). This duty to provide a secure environment for disclosing information reflects the central principle of the Refugee Convention, namely, *non-refoulement* (Home Office, 2015a, pp.4–5). Guidance suggests that in the interview process the principles of the benefit of the doubt and a low standard of proof should apply: “It is low because of what is potentially at stake – the individual’s life or liberty” (Home Office, 2015a, p.11). Thus, the interviews should allow those seeking protection to reveal sensitive evidence that inherently involves highly personal and traumatic details, which can involve civil war, torture, sexual abuse and the death of close relatives and friends. Home Office guidance urges case workers that “you must also be mindful of the effects that the impact of torture or trauma can have on the memory and recall of people who have experienced it as well as the impact the claimant’s cultural and educational background may have” (Home Office, 2018a, p.12).

However, the themes established in Home Office discourse – urging an “open and relaxed and non-threatening” atmosphere (Home Office, 2019a, p.10) – exist in tension with other narratives and policy agendas linked to the asylum system, such as immigration control. Accomplishing these other priorities implies a stance of doubt, suspicion and even “hostility”, a psychology that is not easily reconciled with the openness suggest in official guidance. The experiences of RESPOND interviewees testify to these conflicts: “The immigration officer was extremely rude, rude in a way that it was hard for me to talk about these things [i.e. experiences of persecution]...she was not very nice (PKM01 micro-level interview)”. Another testified:

Of course, it [the interviewer’s behaviour] wasn’t civilized as I am saying now. It was like shouty way. It was super bad...it wasn’t pleasant...I said, “I am really sorry, I apologise, I think there is a misunderstanding, I said this and he interpreted this”. So the lady did not shout, she screamed at me, saying, “You are not allowed to speak to me directly! You have to speak to the interpreter and the interpreter will speak to me!” I was like, “No, the interpreter is interpreting wrong and if he is interpreting wrong I will stop him and I would speak to you directly (SYM02 micro-level interview)

These reports, of behaviour described variously as “shouty”, “rude”, and even “screaming”, represent one extreme of the conflict between immigration control and international protection functions. The system makes the case worker an institutional expression accountable to formal international standards and to widespread perceptions of the asylum system as being a source of illegal immigration. Such considerations are outlined in guidance to case workers:

The UK is committed to providing protection to those who need it, in accordance with its international obligations. Those who fear persecution should however claim asylum and stay in the first safe country they reach and not put their lives at risk by making unnecessary and dangerous journeys to the UK. Illegal migration from safe countries undermines our efforts to help those most in need (Home Office, 2019c, p.5).

Case workers are tasked with resolving these contradictions in practice. Their behaviour likely stems from a perception that a claimant is behaving evasively or misleadingly, which researchers would link to the culture of disbelief (see above). However, as the Home Office observe (e.g. Home Office, 2018a, p.12), perceived equivocation can also reflect the asylum seeker's response to traumatic experiences, including the organised mistrust inherent in the asylum system. One refugee respondent reflected on this:

Imagine some people, they have that level of trauma, they don't know how to describe themselves. I hate to describe myself, for example. Some people, because of, I don't know the reason, their culture, their education, the environment...you've been put before the interview, after the interview, and the gossip and spreading the words about the interview process, makes you shocked, and sometimes you go into the interview and you don't know how to say, "I'm from this part and I'm..." They say, no, you lie, because you just know how to answer this question. It's not right. (IQM01 micro-level interview).

These stories reflect wider reports of refugee experiences, and must be considered in the context of the high volume of erroneous rejections of applications for protection. They are thus reflections of the *systematic* nature of immigration control and narratives of suspicion within the asylum system. Earlier investigations by Amnesty International found that, in a random sample of initial decisions overturned on appeal, 80 percent were grounded in flawed credibility assessments (Amnesty International, 2013, p.32). Research by Refugee Action (2018, p.17) shows that asylum seekers are kept poorly informed and have little chance to prepare themselves for the interview.

Increasingly, in the context of "disbelief" and the "hostile environment", interview evidence alone is distrusted has been downgraded in favour of the more "neutral" testimony of country and medical experts (Sigona, 2014, p.374). Those who had undergone interviews showed awareness that their testimonies were doubted and that judgement of their case was connected to a wider immigration control agenda (see below). Some also contrasted the hostility they encountered from case workers with their initial expectations about the UK's "humanitarian" culture. The interview experience is thus often the first place, where asylum seekers encounter the conflict between the established narrative of the UK's commitment to the rule of law, individual liberty and human rights, on the one hand; and the culture of immigration control, on the other.

Role of Interpreters/Language Barriers

Among the key aspects of the interview experience are the actor's sense of alienation within the asylum system and the role of case workers as analysts of behaviour, ambivalently balancing between control and protection functions. These themes can be further illustrated in a topic that arose repeatedly in micro-level interviews namely (mis)interpretation and linguistic barriers.

Interpretation plays a complex role in the UK's system of refugee status determination (Gibb and Good, 2014) and UNHCR guidance notes that "interpreters can influence – wittingly or unwittingly – the course and the success of an interview" (Krainz and Bergaus, 2017, p.27). The minimum requirement for interpretation is set out in the Procedures Directive 2005: "The communication need not necessarily take place in the language preferred by the applicant for asylum if there is another language that he/she reasonably be supposed to understand [sic] and in which he/she is able to communicate" (Council Directive 2005/85/EC). However, there is considerable ambiguity in terms such as "reasonably...supposed to understand", the criterion also formally reflected in Immigration Rules 339ND and in Home Office guidance. Campaign groups thus note significant gaps in the UK system "leading to sub-standard interviews and, in some cases, incorrect decisions that cause people considerable anguish and may take time – and resources – to correct"

(Refugee Action, 2018, p.18), but it is almost impossible to prove that these are technically breaches of directives.

In several cases, interviewees reported potentially serious flaws in interpretation due to linguistic or cultural misunderstandings:

And after I read the report that he translated I noticed that the questions were different than what the interpreter asked me [in Arabic during the interview]. He changed the questions. At that time my English was not very good so I could not notice that he changed the questions...I told Home Office I understand his Arabic, but he did not translate your questions correctly into Arabic...But they said you have no evidence for this... (IQF01 micro-level interview)

When I applied for asylum...I told the interpreter that I did not understand him well because he spoke Sorani Kurdish. He said, "That is not important. In this interview, we just want to know your name, etc." And it was so difficult to talk to him. At the [substantive] interview they said: "You said this, this and this." And I said, "No, I did not say that, they just put it down." It was really annoying... [The interpreter] just answered as he wanted... (IQM02 micro-level interview).

The first time I applied I used an interpreter with me. Why? It was a case for your life [i.e., a matter of life and death]; you have to explain everything...I don't think he translated well, because many times it was a negotiation between me and the interpreter, correcting for him because he really does not know my language (IQM03 micro-level interview).

Inaccurate interpretation, in these instances, could have led case workers to falsely conclude that the stories were inconsistent. Given that verbal inconsistencies, or discrepancies between verbal testimony and written documents or country of origin information, are central mechanisms for assessing the "credibility" of applicants (Home Office, 2015a), there is significant risk attached to misinterpretation or miscommunication. Indeed, researchers have also noted that even correct, verbatim interpretation presents the possibility for cross-cultural misunderstandings (Gibb and Good, 2014; Kälin, 2017).

These are specific reflections of a broader theme of alienation in the asylum experience, since most claimants will be negotiating a new language and set of cultural circumstances under circumstances of suspicion and "disbelief" (see below). The RESPOND interviews demonstrated that many refugees are highly aware of the possibility that they will be misunderstood when they speak in English, and many expressed the belief that linguistic slips would be used to criminalise them:

They [Home Office] try to play with you until you make a mistake and then they will tell you made a mistake. And this is their job and system and you come to a new country, system and language and you do not know what to do and what not to do...The English officer, I did not understand him well because of his accent. I think that they have to explain more and what rights you have (IQM02 micro-level interview).

They put me in the van with lots of other people. We were very scared to ask questions, this is not good; we are scared, we are not confident. If you know a little bit of English, you try to help others. But you miscommunicate, you try to help them but it's not the right way to do it (IQM01 micro-level interview).

There were no interpreters there at all. Unfortunately, all the communication was in English and we couldn't understand what they were saying. It was fine at the police station in the airport, there was an interpreter, but in that [detention centre] prison, they really treated us like war prisoners. I used to use a friend called [name] for a bit of interpreting, asking him to help me so that I won't answer a yes or no by mistake and then lose all my life. The treatment over

there was very bad, it was, I am sorry, similar to the treatment in the Iranian prisons (INM01 micro-level interview).

In the quotes above, in different contexts, those claiming asylum frame themselves in an antagonistic relationship with state officials. Rather than being engaged in the pursuit of protection in a cooperative fashion, as the humanitarian narrative suggests, they instead picture themselves as under surveillance and scrutiny over small behavioural details and slips of the tongue which could have life-threatening consequences. Thus, the perception of danger attached to the prospect of misinterpretation was heightened by their consciousness of surrounding political and policy narratives. Several interviewees linked their fears of miscommunication specifically to the longstanding perception of criminality, threat or “bogusness” attached to those seeking asylum, showing explicit awareness of notions such as the “hostile environment”.

I kind of made it my mission to know more about the legal system, so I started studying about it. I started learning about the Home Office. It was UK Border Agency at the time. I mean, how the UK Borders Agency goes about their cases, what's their quota, how many people get asylum status granted, what's the standard procedure, the Hostile Environment, a number of things. Then everything started making sense. The more I learn about it, the less hopeful I was (PKM01 micro-level interview).

This quote represents an advanced and explicit case of the broader phenomenon where those who undergo the asylum system come to know and internalise the surrounding government narratives. The risk of linguistic misunderstanding, which is part of most immigrant experiences, becomes particularly critical when actors are forced to adapt to an established narrative that delegitimises, criminalises and stigmatises their status.

Geographical Barriers to Accessing the Asylum System

Article 6 of the 2005 Procedures Directive gives (minimal) standards for allowing applicants access to the asylum system, including the suggestion that “Member States may require that applications for asylum be made in person and/or at a designated place”. Barriers to access may take many forms some of which arose during RESPOND interviews and are explored in this chapter such as vulnerability, communication barriers and absence of information. However, in RESPOND interviews, *geographical barriers* were also identified as a significant issue, which reflects growing research attention to the “connection and disconnection between different sites, practices and assemblages through which asylum and refugee governance is achieved” (Gill, 2010, p.638, see also 2009).

Only roughly ten percent of applicants access the asylum system at the port of entry (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.18). The main options for “in country” applications are to make an application from inside detention, or to attend at the Asylum Intake Unit (AIU) in Croydon, Greater London (see Home Office, 2018a, pp.23–4). Exceptions to this only happen in extreme circumstances, and while destitution can be grounds for exemption, this is rarely allowed in practice due to the difficulties of providing destitution in practice (Asylum Information Database, 2018, p.18; Hutton, Simic and Blitz, 2017, p.8). In UK RESPOND’s meso-level interviews with professionals, the requirement of attending in Croydon was identified as a significant barrier. No funds are provided for attendance at AIU, and asylum seekers are unable to claim funds at this stage. Third Sector organisations thus often had to do fundraising to cover the costs of the trip:

People, who arrive in Scotland, for example, unless you arrive in an airport and know to claim asylum in the airport or you’re a child or have a very extreme vulnerability, you’ll be put on an overnight bus to Croydon to claim asylum. And the voluntary sector has to pay for that because otherwise people would be

destitute. They'd be left destitute and unable to access the asylum determination process despite the fact that there's an expectation that people will apply as soon as reasonably practicable (meso level interview with voluntary sector manager).

[T]here is no funding to going to Croydon necessarily, and it's not an easy thing to navigate by yourself....so we think that introducing that rule is really effectively a barrier to the access to the asylum process. And one that causes further problems as well, because where there is a delay it can be held against the claimant (meso level interview with Just Right Scotland).

I suppose the major issue for us is that people who are in Scotland who want to claim asylum can't, apart from in some very specific circumstances they can't claim and have their initial screening here. They have to go to Croydon which you know for people you know who are in Scotland is a quite a long way to go and difficult journey, particularly those who haven't been here very long and don't know the country (meso level interview with Scottish Government official).

The fact that you have to lodge your initial claim in Croydon is very bizarre and definitely discriminates against anyone who can't afford, who has childcare issues or mobility issues to have to go all the way to Croydon (meso level interview with Scottish Green Party councillor).

There was a strong belief, therefore, that the requirement of registering in Croydon was anomalous and a barrier to access that caused significant psychological distress. The anxiety caused by the lengthy trip was also identified in micro-level interviews with those who had experienced the system:

In the first interview in Croydon, you know, you are already anxious. You don't know what are you expecting and the whole journey to Croydon is really disturbing (SYM02 micro-level interview).

Beyond the emotional and practical inconvenience of the journey, the physical architecture and layout of the Croydon facility itself was identified as a factor:

I went to Croydon, as soon as I entered the building that was a bit of a shocker. I would say for the first time I felt a bit intimidated. Not in a way, because I've never committed any crime or done anything or what you expect someone who has done something wrong to be treated, in a way. Getting frisked, people going through your stuff (PKM01 micro-level interview)

The inconveniences attached to the Croydon experience – the intimidating length of the trip, its costs, and the requirement to attend promptly – were identified as “tactics...to make the asylum as inaccessible as possible”.

Obviously, you can only claim asylum at a port, really, or in a centralised spot in Croydon, which is obviously a deliberate tactic by the Home Office to make the asylum system as inaccessible as possible. It isn't really in the spirit of the Charter, either, I'd say. Other than that, it's just the Home Office's objective is making things as inaccessible as possible (meso level interview with community project worker).

For this interviewee, “inaccessibility” is not accidental or merely an efficiency measure but rather part of the set of tactical manoeuvres used to fulfil pledges of immigration control. This was a theme suggested in several meso-level interviews. Another interpretation would be to link the centralisation of services to the programme of cost-cutting and efficiency with the asylum system regarded as an unnecessary “burden” to the taxpayer coming at the expense of other public services (e.g. Darling, 2016). In both cases, the atmosphere of fear and anxiety that surrounds the asylum experience at Croydon is linked to broader societal narratives about managing immigration.

Delays

Mistakes, delays, and maladministration are seen as routine elements of the UK asylum system (Firth and Clayton, 2018, p.427). The most notable effect of this, in the asylum experience, is long periods of time spent waiting as claims (and appeals) are processed. There are conflicts over what constitutes a maximum acceptable time period for examining asylum cases, but six months is often used as a benchmark. This timeframe is mentioned in both iterations of the Procedures Directive, although it is asserted more forcefully in the second phase (to which the UK is not a signatory) than in the first. In 2014, the Home Office committed to deciding 98 percent of standard asylum claims within six months, but by 2019 this target was officially abandoned: only 75 percent of decisions were being made within the six month target as of 2017, meaning that nearly 15,000 cases lasted longer (Allison and Taylor, 2019).

These intervals of waiting on decisions with little ability to participate in mainstream society are experienced as particularly isolating. Research by refugee campaigners finds that delays are among the most traumatic parts of the overall experience with one report stating the following. "The process had dehumanised and disempowered them to such an extent that they spoke of feeling hopeless and having no control over the situation they found themselves in" (RAS Voice, 2017, p.2; see also Refugee Action, 2018, pp.32–5). The experience of delays has significant practical as well as emotional consequences. The British Red Cross has reported that of the 6,000 cases they receive reporting as destitute every year half are caused by administrative failings or delays in the system (UK Government, 2013, p.37). Serious impacts on mental health are reported by campaign groups (e.g. MIND, 2009) and reflected in the RESPOND interviewees:

[I]t took about 1.5 years until I got an answer. They delayed the date of my court a lot. During this time one would become a bit depressed and a bit isolated...They give me a court date for after a year then and it got cancelled also once or twice so it took 1.5 year to get a reply and so it affected my emotional/mental state quite a lot...The more I heard about other people's experiences of the courts, I got more scared and I was lonely too (INM02 micro-level interview).

Those who undergo the appeals system are particularly affected by the uncertainty of delays:

I start my asylum process, which is usually find a lawyer or some charity organisation or refugee organisation, help you find lawyer. Interview, fail. Interview, fail. Go to court, fail. Go to court, fail. Interview, fail. All these circles... Deportation, wait, and do that, do that, lots of appeals, then finally, my case was accepted by Home Office. I was on the way to go to High Court, when I appealed, and they say, "Yeah, okay, there you go after two years, three years, there you go (IQM01 micro-level interview).

Every time you apply and get refused. After that I did interview, waited 2 months and they said it was refused. I have right at that time to appeal. I appealed and it took 10 months to go to court and it was refused. This was refused in 2015. And since then all of my applications have been refused. It was a nightmare for all of us, you cannot do anything... [The] situation gets worse because you are not allowed to work, you don't have enough income for your family for a holiday or anything, not even in the UK. You cannot take your family to a different city...because of economic reasons you cannot take them and enjoy a holiday elsewhere (IQM03 micro-level interview).

These two interviews illustrate different stages of undergoing a protracted decision with the first having received status after a wait of two or three years while the second remains within the system. The first uses the metaphor of circles of repetition. The second narrates the process as a “nightmare” of waiting without work on an extreme low income and being unable to travel. Both suggested that the claimants feel trapped by the machinery of administration.

As with the geographical barriers discussed above, protracted administrative barriers and delays can be interpreted either as a *strategy* linked to narratives of immigration control, or as an unintentional effect of wider processes of austerity. In either case, this manifests in the experience of asylum seekers as uncertainty, fear and alienation from the system.

Detention

Related to the theme of delays, detention plays a central role in the British system: the UK is one of only a few countries in the Council of Europe not to put an upper time limit on immigration detention (APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015, p.16). Detention is at the discretion of immigration officers acting on behalf of the Secretary of State, rather than of a judge or a court, and there is no legal requirement for detention orders to undergo judicial review (Home Affairs Committee, 2019, p.9).

The rate of detention has increased markedly in recent decades and an estate of detention centres has grown in parallel (this is covered in-depth in WP2: see Karamanidou, 2019). These centres have been focuses of serious disturbances with riots at Yarl’s Wood in 2002 and Harmondsworth in both 2004 and 2006 causing near total destruction of the buildings (Shaw, 2016, p.30). Many, who ultimately gain protection status, including some of our interviewees, will have undergone sometimes extended periods in immigration detention. According to the Detention Centre Rules 2001, which govern the process, the process should involve “the secure but humane accommodation of detained persons in a relaxed regime with as much freedom of movement and association as possible, consistent with maintaining a safe and secure environment, and to encourage and assist detained persons to make the most productive use of their time, whilst respecting in particular their dignity and the right to individual expression” (The Detention Centre Rules 2001). However, themes of criminalisation dominated all the detention narratives in micro-level interviews: “I was just moved from police station, prison, to another prison called detention centre” (IQM01 micro-level interview). Other testified:

For nine months I was stuck there in the detention centre [in a] very tiny room... I am treated like a criminal. I'm claiming asylum and sometimes I'm thinking that I've done a very big crime (PKM02 micro-level interview).

It was a proper prison and when I saw that I was shocked, especially after the bad experiences of being in prison in Iran... I asked, “Where is this place?” They said, “It’s prison”, so I thought, “Why should I be in prison, I am only an asylum-seeker” (INM01 micro-level interview).

Again, it's uncertainty. You don't know what's going on after that. Will they send me back to my terrible country? Will they leave me here for months, years? Or what's going to happen? Where am I going? It's uncertainty, and just worrying, stress, trauma... Sometimes indescribable, and you only think, I only hope, I hope I will leave this room (IQM01 micro-level interview).

The link between administrative detention and criminality has been formally recognised. Indeed, an official UK Parliamentary has concluded the following. “We are concerned at the increasing use of detention centres that make use of conditions tantamount to high security prison settings to detain people” (APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015, p.42). It is reflected in the geography of detention: the UK’s five largest detention centres are either

former prisons or have been built to Category B prison standards (APPG Refugees and APPG Migration, 2015, p.42). As a Government commissioned report observed, the growing “reliance upon prison places...is a creation of the 21st Century, and the drive to increase the number of removals of people with no right to remain in this country” (Shaw, 2016, p.31).

Although families with children are an exception to this rule, narratives surrounding the detention system are normally very explicitly linked to immigration control, with fewer attempts at humanitarian rationalisation compared to the other themes discussed in this chapter. The general ambivalence of UK Government asylum policy with its balance between deterrence and humanitarian narratives tends to be diminished when it comes to detention, since those entering the system are suspected of a “clearly unfounded” claim or have otherwise been deemed to have forfeited their right to protection.

Resettlement Schemes

The biggest post-2011 change in the UK protection structure has been the emergence of resettlement schemes centred largely, if not exclusively, around Syrian refugees (see section on developments since 2011). By normal comparisons, these have received considerable support with local authorities able to claim up to £20,520 per refugee towards services over their first five years in the UK (Hough, 2018, p.10). In meso-level interviews, respondents reflected that these schemes had a positive reputation for providing a better standard of protection and reception services, and for involving a greater range of partners especially local authorities:

Yes, it’s certainly the one that’s talked about as the gold standard and there’s certainly more resources in there for provision for more intensive support...You know, there’s an assumption that [resettlement programmes are] really good but actually to what extent that’s been critically evaluated I don’t know (meso level interview with voluntary sector manager).

And, it’s very good that that resettlement programme exists in the UK because it gives us something to look at to use as a standard because it is way better and much better funded for five years actually, which not a lot of people know than the asylum seeker system that people come into, so it’s good in that respect but it’s actually not touching very many people (meso level interview with Asylum Seeker Housing Project).

Even where interviewees reported the positive reputation of resettlement programmes – “gold standard”, “intensive support”, “much better funded” – they are qualified by concerns about lack of critical evaluation and the small numbers that gain from them. Praise for the resettlement system is thus used on a comparative basis to highlight flaws in the normal asylum. However, some framed the “success” of the resettlement programme in a more critical manner.

[The UK] hardly brings anyone through resettlement. It creates a two-tier system...Well, there’s an implied moral hierarchy of migration and even though resettlement is seen to be, you know, the legitimate way for refugees to come to this country, hardly anyone’s actually brought through (meso level interview with voluntary sector manager).

Thus, the humanitarian narrative surrounding resettlement, and the range of (comparatively) effective local services provided on that basis can work to delegitimise those who enter the normal asylum procedure, creating a “two-tier system” based on “an implied moral hierarchy”. This links back to the narratives established in the previous section, with categories of vulnerability used to reinforce narratives of deterrence for asylum claimants deemed less legitimate and less worthy. Humanitarian narratives can be used by critics of the Government, including its Parliamentary critics, as a standard to judge the practices of

the UK system. However, it can also work to reclassify and “other” certain groups applying within the protection system. Similarly, some interviewees framed the resettlement scheme as an opportunity for critical reflection on other parts of the system; others framed it as a potential mechanism for justifying a reduction in services elsewhere by reinforcing narratives of “bogusness” and migration reduction.

Vulnerability

Within an international protection context, the concept of “vulnerability” can be used in two distinct senses. On the one hand, “asylum seekers are vulnerable *per se*” (UNHCR, 2013, p.9), so the term can refer in undifferentiated terms to the precarious nature of the asylum experience. On the other hand, the concept is also commonly used to demarcate special classes of asylum seekers with distinct needs due to their physical, mental or social circumstances (Asylum Information Database, 2017, p.7). Article 20 of the first-round Qualifications Directive specifically lists “minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled people, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children and persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence” (Council Directive 2004/83/EC) as classes of vulnerable people. In recent British discourse and policy practice, there has been a particular focus on victims of human trafficking, which Theresa May described as the “greatest human rights issue of our time”. The Home Office produces special procedural guidance for case workers that focus on particular categories of vulnerability, such as gender issues or sexual identity (e.g. Home Office, 2018b, 2016).

As explained in the narratives section, academic researchers have expressed reservations about the concept of vulnerability in asylum discourse. Meso-level practitioner interviews highlighted similar concerns:

I think ‘vulnerable’ is an overused term in social work settings generally. It gets thrown around...Everyone we see has been to hell and back. Our focus is: ‘what is the help you need, and can we give it to you’. We don’t dwell on the vulnerable. We dwell on problems and how we can help (meso level interview with Asylum Welcome group).

This interview highlights the gap between the universal nature of vulnerability – “everyone we see has been to hell and back” – and the term’s use in professional contexts as a label of demarcation to establish a hierarchy of need. The term “vulnerability”, in this perspective, has been degraded by its function in official policy discourse, making it suitable for a particular order of professionals but less useful when managing the everyday needs of asylum seekers. This reinforces researchers’ reservations about the term, highlighted in the narratives section.

Moreover, the implication of the discourse is that asylum systems are functioning to cure a pre-existing condition of vulnerability. However, the term can be used in the opposite sense, with vulnerability *being imposed by the asylum system*:

I feel like the system makes people vulnerable, so even people that are usually very resilient and everyone I’ve met is very resilient and has survived, you know, the people that have survived enough to get here are the people with extremely high levels of resilience. But even then, the system is just so cruel that it just...breaks people so... I’m not sure who is not vulnerable in the current system and it definitely re-traumatizes people (meso level interview with Scottish Green Party councillor).

This repeats the concern above that vulnerability has become less useful in practice due to its official usage as a classification of specific groups: “I’m not sure who is not vulnerable

in the current system”. Moreover, in this practitioner’s experience, the system, rather than building resilience the system breaks down existing sources of resilience built from the survival of trauma and “re-traumatizes people”.

The gaps in the vulnerability discourse may also be considered from the opposite perspective. Despite official commitments to prioritise specific vulnerable groups, members of these groups continue to suffer particular inequalities within the system. There is a specific section on gender below, so the following quotes concern other aspects of vulnerability, such as LGBTQ* status and disability:

And things around sexuality, there was this horrendous thing that I came across at some point. It was a gay man from Afghanistan and the Home Office decision maker had found a press story [in which] there’s a kind of custom in some bits of Afghanistan where young boys under fourteen dance for older men and are basically sexually abused by them, and the decision maker said ok, we’ve found evidence of this practice which shows that actually opinions towards homosexuality are not as bad as you think... Do you know, just because you are gay doesn’t necessarily mean you have had sex with somebody of the same gender so you are being asked very sexually explicit questions to try and prove your sexuality (meso level interview with former employee of Red Cross).

I mean, there’s things around when it comes to accommodation and how people are accommodated if someone has a disability, in my experience that is often not accommodated so you might get somebody who is has crutches and is housed three floors up and it is very difficult to them get them moved. And also, people with mental health issues who would be much better off being accommodated on their own are accommodated with other people. Ah, travel to, travelling about, so you don’t get, in theory you should get your hospital, if you’re travelling to a medical appointment you can get, claim expenses but as far as I know that is on a reclaiming basis so if you don’t have the money upfront (meso level interview with former employee of Red Cross).

These experiences reflect the long-established conclusion that the UK asylum system has enforced institutional injustices against “vulnerable” groups (Bachmann, 2016; Dyck, 2019; Yeo, 2017b). In practice, the experience of particular vulnerabilities, such as disability, emerges against the backdrop of the wider policy context of restrictions within the asylum system. Thus, while there are guidelines to prevent active discrimination, the key problem may be experiencing disability in the context of poverty: since the Immigration and Asylum Act 1999 removed the right to claim welfare benefits, into allowances for disability. Moreover, while there are minimal discretionary payments available for disabled claimants, this reinforces the perception of these as “gifts” rather than rights with clear criteria of entitlement (Yeo, 2017b, p.263).

In understanding the role of vulnerability in the UK system, it is necessary on the one hand to address the rhetorical use of the concept, as covered in the narratives section. In political discourse, vulnerability has been linked to immigration control and the delegitimisation of spontaneously-arriving asylum seekers. On the other hand, the concept has been linked to valid aims: for example, there have been longstanding criticisms of the UK system for its failure to address the specific nature of gender-based persecution and for imposing gender inequality (see below). Again, the difficulty arises because this protection agenda becomes entwined with the separate aim of immigration control.

Gender

Gender-based experiences have been crucial to the UK narrative of vulnerability, as demonstrated in the narratives section. Failure to account for gender issues has been a

common criticism of the Convention legal framework (e.g. Crawley, 2000), although there has been guidance produced for interpreting gender-based persecution (UNHCR, 2002). UK policy draws from other sources of international law. This includes the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW); the Council of Europe Convention on preventing and combating violence against women and domestic violence; and the relevant sections of the Qualification and Procedures Directives, both of which have been transposed into UK law (Home Office, 2018b, pp.11–12). Furthermore, there is a range of UK-specific legislation that is officially focused on outlawing gender-based discrimination. Home Office documentation references, in this regard, the Equality Act 2010 plus more specific provisions such as the Female Genital Mutilation (FGM) Act 2003 and the Anti-social Behaviour, Crime and Policing Act 2014, which outlaws forced marriage (Home Office, 2018b, p.13). The UK has also implemented an Ending Violence against Women and Girls strategy which makes specific provisions for the asylum system (HM Government, 2016, p.40).

However, these policies have emerged against a backdrop of acknowledged failure to take account of gender-specific circumstances. A report by Asylum Aid found that a disproportionately high number of initial asylum claim rejections for women were subsequently overturned on appeal, a conclusion accepted by what was then the UK Borders Agency (Asylum Aid, 2011, p.5). One respondent, commenting on these statistics, noted

Female asylum claimants might have a lower level of education, are less able to articulate their claim, or prosecute their claim, and single female headed households will also struggle with things like childcare for the children during the asylum interview or to attend legal appointments, so there are kind of process reasons and legal reason why I think, the higher rate of failure of female asylum claims suggest that there is no adequate protection in the British asylum system (meso level interview with Just Right Scotland).

Studies have also demonstrated that the vulnerability of women entering the asylum system can be especially acute. Research on women detained in the UK asylum system, with a sample size of 46, found that 87 percent had been tortured or raped, 61 percent had considered killing themselves, and 52 percent had claimed asylum having being specifically persecuted as a woman (Girma et al., 2014, p.14; see also Dorling, Girma and Walter, 2012).

Our meso-level respondents reported that the intersection of gender-based inequality with the precarious nature of the asylum experience, especially in conditions of poverty, led to specific problems:

I'm yet to meet a women yet who is in the system who is not vulnerable at this point but women who have escaped sexual violence, who have been through rape, who have been through forced marriage the coming into contact with a system that is violent and very disempowering, this kind of re-traumatizes them (meso level interview with Scottish Green Councillor).

I had a lady that was given 24 hours' notice until she was going to be evicted and she was like a single mum, she had four kids all under eight one of whom was profoundly autistic and like, she'd fled domestic abuse. So, she's fled persecution and then when she was here she was still with her abuse husband so she managed to get away from him with the help of Women's Aid and had just sort of started out on her own and then got this letter saying by 12 noon tomorrow you have got to be out of your accommodation and we'll change the locks and so she was like out of her mind and the letter had no email address and had no phone number and it just had a fax. Who has a fax? You know, it's just, I've never seen a fax machine. So, she was advised by social work to call Migrant Help and you know, couldn't get through there and social work yelled at

her which wasn't great, yelled at me, which wasn't great (meso level interview with Scottish Green Councillor).

In the last example, the extra expectations on women looking after children, under specific conditions of gendered oppression (domestic abuse), add to the standard experience of precarity that surrounds the asylum experience. This reinforces the point, made above with regard to vulnerability, that putting in place specific policies for to help "vulnerable" groups access the system does not necessarily help all members of that group. Due to the family and other responsibilities socially ascribed to women, the experience of poverty and inadequate service provision continue to present barriers to the claiming the protection rights that manifested in gendered inequalities.

Gender-based experience also includes masculinity. One male respondent showed particular awareness of the experience of women, contrasting his own (often severe) experiences with theirs.

I've seen people, friends, colleagues, been through worse than my experience...Manipulated by agents, went to prison, been abused, lots of horrible things happen to them, because they have the money, or sometimes because they don't have the money, because they are a woman...They have been through a lot, violence, rape, abuse, lots of so many horrible things...[I]f you are in a vulnerable position, if you are not a man, if you are not strong, even if you are a man, if you're not having people around you, it's worse. Especially if you are a woman, you are pretty, lots of horrible things. They try to make fun of vulnerability, whatever (IQM01 micro-level interview).

As the respondent suggests, there are particular "vulnerabilities" that women experience during the journey and within the asylum system. The respondent shows sensitivity towards gender issues, but also asserts an equation of masculinity with strength. However, he qualifies this statement by suggesting that men, in circumstances of enforced isolation, experience vulnerability too. The idea(l) of masculinity implies the absence of vulnerability, but the stereotype is unlikely to apply to everyone. Moreover, the extreme circumstances of the asylum system meant that men interviewed for the project would admit to non-"masculine" vulnerable behaviours:

I had to cry in front of the woman (staff) at the job centre and then she felt sorry for me and said, Ok we will pay your benefits from the next month (INM01 micro-level interview).

They say, "If you don't pay, we won't treat you, or give you the treatment, and you cannot come back here again, because you have not paid the £20 invoice". They say, "It's not our problem". And I just fell very very sad, emotional, I went to Refugee Council and I just cried. They said, "Don't worry, don't worry, we'll help you". But I'm not crying because...It's humiliating, really, you cannot get treatment because you don't have cash. Why don't you have cash? Because the Home Office or the system prefers not giving you cash (IQM01 micro-level interview).

Brexit and the Future of International Protection

The UK's approach to international protection has been shaped in various ways by its membership of the European Union. Since the 2016 "Brexit" referendum, where the public voted narrowly to leave the EU, the future form of relationship has been uncertain. The UK Government triggered Article 50 on leaving the European Union in March 2017, but since then the initial deadline has been extended twice. Options continue to range from the restoration of full UK membership of the EU to a complete break with all of its structures in a so-called "No Deal" scenario. In any circumstance that involves the UK leaving, it will be in a unique situation as a third country with a longstanding history of cooperation with the EU in the field of international protection (Gutheil et al., 2018, p.81).

Immigration has been a highly politicised part of these debates (Virdee and McGeever, 2018), and the asylum system has been problematized insofar as there is a longstanding tendency in UK politics to conflate international protection with the "problem" of migration management. The politicisation takes both simple and complex forms. Leave campaigners argued that Brexit would allow the UK to "take back control" – a theme usually linked to immigration. Since the vote, Remain campaigners have warned of a more authoritarian, nationalistic turn with the UK becoming a "weak link" on international protections. Equally, though, other prominent supporters of the European Union, such as former Prime Minister Tony Blair, have proposed multilateral, Europe-wide initiatives to harden European external borders and reduce non-European migration into the continent (Blair, 2017).

The issues highlighted by Blair's position – which resemble David Cameron's initial agreement for continued EU membership – are a reminder of the UK's multifaceted relationship with the EU on matters of migration management and international protection. Simplistic contrasts between liberal Europhilia and authoritarian nationalism neither capture the full complexity of discourses nor the geopolitical tensions underlying EU-UK relations. For example, the task of policing borders and controlling migration have increasingly depend on multilateral cooperation, particularly with EU systems including Dublin, biometric/fingerprinting data and external agreements on migration controls with countries like Turkey and Libya.

Since the referendum and the triggering of Article 50, there have been only limited indications of how the UK and the EU will evolve a new relationship on international protection. One systematic research study, assessing the future relationship from an EU perspective, has been published, although it does not necessarily represent EU policy and only makes general recommendations (Gutheil et al., 2018). The UK Government previously published a White Paper on the future relationship, and agreed both a Withdrawal Agreement and a Political Declaration to this end with the EU. However, these documents contain little detail on matters of international protection, and now no longer represent UK Government policy.

To gain a more accurate perspective, the starting point should be how the EU actually affects the UK's international protection system. Partly this is about human rights with the enforcement of minimum protections offered under the first-round CEAS directives and the EU's Charter of Fundamental Rights. However, other European mechanisms have *consequences* for international protection but are more accurately framed as forms of migration management or, at maximum, as straddling the boundary between protection and control. These include the Dublin III and Eurodac, the EU Readmission Agreements, plus the UK's cooperation with Frontex.

In regard to ensuring protection, the Qualification, Reception and Procedures Directives have become part of UK law. There has been no indication that the UK plans to abandon these minimum standards and leaked Home Office documents on the future of the migration system suggest that removing existing CEAS provisions is not a priority (The Guardian,

2017b; Yeo, 2017a). However, theoretically the principle of sovereignty (and “taking back control”) could override these instruments in future. Asylum seekers are also protected by wider instruments such as the European Convention on Human Rights (the Human Rights Act in UK law) and the EU Charter. The UK Government has stated that it will withdraw from the Charter, but will remain bound by the ECHR (a provision of the Council of Europe rather than the EU). Theoretically, the Charter offers some additional protections compared to the Convention. In reality, the main recourse in asylum cases is to the European Court of Human Rights (governing the Convention) rather than to the Court of Justice of the EU (governing the Charter), so the actual implications for international protection may not be significant (Gutheil et al., 2018, p.54). Nonetheless, as established in Section XXX, while the UK remains formally committed to the ECHR, Conservative politicians have regularly expressed their desire to leave its jurisdiction and establish instead a UK “Bill of Rights”.

However, the current agenda of international protection includes not just ensuring the rights of individuals, but also “burden sharing” and migration management issues. On these issues, the UK has taken more explicit stances on cooperation. The White Paper on the *Future Relationship between the United Kingdom and the European Union* suggested that they would “establish a new, strategic relationship to address the global challenges of asylum and illegal migration” (Department for Exiting the European Union, 2018c, p.70). The draft Political Declaration mentions measures to “strengthen the [European] Union’s external border” and “to tackle illegal migration upstream” (Department for Exiting the European Union, 2018b, p.21). Similarly, the draft Withdrawal Agreement says the UK will honour commitments to EU funds for “stability and addressing root causes of irregular migration and displaced persons in Africa” and to the Facility for Refugees in Turkey (Department for Exiting the European Union, 2018a, p.263). The UK’s commitment to externalising the management of migration flows (including those who plan to seek asylum) has often depended on cooperation with EU agencies.

There is thus an inherent contradiction in the more radical “Brexit” proposals for breaking with European structures in favour of sovereignty and national control. Contemporary efforts to control and limit migration (and thus also flows of protection-seekers) are very often multilateral enterprises. The UK will have freedom to establish new geopolitical relationships; however, as one report observes, “none of the existing legal mechanisms and policy measures which are used to support the cooperation between the EU and other third countries in the field of international protection are exactly replicable for the UK.” The contrast between “open” Europeanism and “closed” nationalism, implied in many politicised responses, is therefore misleading.

Nonetheless, the process of leaving the EU does pose certain risks to international protection rights. The palette of potential legal safeguards will be slightly diminished, particularly if the UK leaves abruptly in a “No Deal Brexit”. Moreover, the politicisation of sovereignty and borders can have widespread repercussions that have implications for asylum seekers alongside other BME communities, as the “Hostile Environment” has proven.

Conclusion

The UK's approach to international protection is complicated by its longstanding link to narratives and policies of immigration control. Attempts to reconcile humanitarian commitments with promises of drastic reductions in migration have produced contradictory outcomes. There is a risk of a "two tier" system with resettlement programmes having moral and financial precedence over the standard asylum system. Equally, it is unclear in practice that the system benefits the "vulnerable" groups targeted in the humanitarian discourses of British governments. At best, the stress on helping vulnerable groups is helping to overcome historic biases against groups such as women and LGBTQ* claimants. However, the reduction of support services, third sector funding and welfare, added to the "culture of disbelief", may reinforce the difficulties faced by these vulnerable groups.

Other notable conclusions include:

- The UK system has been characterised by significant delays and administration problems. This has been a particular source of anxiety for those claiming asylum, including some of those interviewed by RESPOND.
- Since 2014, largely as a response to events in Syria, the UK has introduced policies to resettle refugees already granted status elsewhere, mainly from conflict-adjacent countries. RESPOND interviews brought out anxieties about an emerging "two-tier system" (see also APPG Refugees, 2017, p.6) and a "moral hierarchy" with refugees benefitting from resettlement programmes (mostly, but not exclusively, Syrians) seen as more legitimate and deserving than spontaneously-arriving claimants.
- Many refugee interviewees claimed that in the interviews that form their main opportunity to present their case, they encountered hostility, obstruction or what was perceived as a stance of entrenched disbelief. However, a few reported positive impressions of the system and encounters with case workers. Inconsistency characterises the experience of the system and adds to the uncertainty that actors experience within it.
- The system was often presented as inaccessible, with numerous inconveniences that were presented both as detrimental to the asylum experience and as inefficient. However, actors took different views of the causes behind this, with some presenting inaccessibility as a deliberate strategy linked to immigration control, while others presented these barriers as unintentional consequences of austerity.
- Many interviewees reported that during the asylum process, their mental health suffered from a mixture of poverty, uncertainty, and fears of being returned. Themes of isolation and alienation from the system and surrounding society were one of the most marked features of the interviews. Their experiences of long periods of detention and waiting within the system were particularly traumatic.

As the previous section has established, firm conclusions about the UK's future framework are difficult to establish amid the uncertainty surrounding Brexit. However, extensive changes to international protection and human rights will only happen if Brexit leads the UK to pursue withdrawal from other instruments such as the ECHR.

Policy Recommendations

Given the findings of this report, the following policy recommendations are made:

- Regardless of Brexit, to maintain protection standards at least at current EU levels, namely the second round of CEAS directives;
- Guarantee that the UK will continue to honour basic human rights commitments such as the ECHR;
- Ensure that resettlement programmes built around the concept of vulnerability do not form the basis of a two-tier system. Instead, a “levelling up” of protection programmes should take place;
- Introduce enforceable time-limits for asylum case processing and ending, or at least time limiting, detention in line with international standards;
- Policies to address vulnerability should acknowledge that poverty, destitution and service cuts are experienced particularly acutely by target groups such as women;
- A clearer functional differentiation between international protection and immigration control;
- Remove barriers to entering the UK with the purpose of claiming asylum;
- Further institutional reviews on the existence of the “(sub)culture of disbelief” among case workers and other officials;
- As emphasised in the previous work package, an end to the Hostile/Compliant Environment framework.

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Appendices

ANNEX I: Important Directives to Consider as a part of the EU legal framework

- **ASYLUM PROCEDURES DIRECTIVE:** establishes common standards of safeguards and guarantees to access a fair and efficient asylum procedure. **The revised Asylum Procedures Directive** aims at fairer, quicker and better-quality asylum decisions. Asylum seekers with special needs will receive the necessary support to explain their claim and in particular there will be greater protection of unaccompanied minors and victims of torture.
- **QUALIFICATION DIRECTIVE:** establishes common grounds for granting international protection and foresees a series of rights for its beneficiaries (residence permits, travel documents, access to employment and education, social welfare and healthcare). **The revised Qualification Directive** clarifies the grounds for granting international protection and therefore will make asylum decisions more robust. It will also improve the access to rights and integration measures for beneficiaries of international protection.
- **TEMPORARY PROTECTION DIRECTIVE:** 20/07/2001 - Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving **temporary protection** in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof

ANNEX II: THE MIDDLE EAST FRAMEWORK FOR INTERNATIONAL PROTECTION

In the Middle East and North Africa, regional human rights instruments relevant to refugee protection include the Arab Charter on Human Rights: the Declaration on the Protection of Refugees and Displaced Persons in the Arab World (adopted Nov.1992); The Arab Convention of Regulating the Status of Refugees in the Arab countries(1994); OIC's Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam (1990); OIC's Ashgabat Declaration (2012); League of Arab States, Protocol for the Treatment of Palestinians in Arab States ("Casablanca Protocol"), 11 September 1965, available at <http://www.refworld.org/docid/460a2b252.html>.

ANNEX III: SOME USEFUL LINKS/REFERENCES

UNHCR statistics, available at http://popstats.unhcr.org/en/asylum_seekers

UNHCR Protection Manual, available at <http://www.refworld.org/protectionmanual.html#header5307550a429-5307550a5af>. [It includes all available legal documents on refugee protection]

Handbook on Procedures and Criteria for Determining Refugee Status under the 1951 Convention and the 1967 Protocol relating to the Status of Refugees HCR/IP/4/Eng/REV.1 Reedited, Geneva, January 1992, UNHCR 1979, available at <http://www.unhcr.org/4d93528a9.pdf>

UNHCR Agenda for Protection, 2008, Third Edition, available at <http://www.unhcr.org/protection/globalconsult/3e637b194/agenda-protection-third-edition.html> (It is a non-binding document adopted by UNHCR and States)

Refugee protection and durable solutions in the context of international migration Report on the High Commissioner's Dialogue on Protection Challenges, December 2007, available at <http://www.unhcr.org/47fe0e532.pdf>

UNHCR Guidelines on Temporary protection 2014: Standards and Indicators in UNHCR Operations, available at <http://www.unhcr.org/40eaa9804.pdf>.

ANNEX IV: COUNTRY LEVEL UNHCR PROTECTION STANDARDS

Country level		
Themes	Sub-themes	Indicators
Access of Asylum-seekers and Refugees to Rights without Discrimination	Access to the territory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have border authorities been clearly instructed to refer asylum-seekers to the competent authority? • Are there credible reports of refoulement?
	Freedom of movement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there cases of unwarranted detention beyond ExCom Conclusion 44?
	Right to documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do all asylum-seekers / refugees have access to individual identity documentation?
	Right to public education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do asylum-seekers / refugees have access to [compulsory and] free primary education? • Are school diplomas / certificates obtained in the country of origin recognized in host country?
	Right to health care	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do asylum-seekers / refugees have access to emergency and primary health care services?
	Access to gainful employment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do all asylum-seekers / refugees have a right to engage in gainful employment?
Refugee Status Determination	Statelessness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do states grant nationality to persons born in the territory of the state, if they would otherwise be stateless? • Are there reported cases of arbitrary deprivation of nationality leading to statelessness? • Do states allow renunciation of nationality only if the person concerned has acquired another nationality? • Are births of non-refugee stateless children properly registered?
	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do all asylum-seekers have access to RSD procedures? • Do all asylum-seekers have access to information and counselling on RSD procedures? • Are reasons for rejection shared in writing with the applicant? • Are applicants permitted to remain in the country while an appeal is pending? • Are rejected asylum-seekers being deported/ repatriated? • Average processing time between submission of application and first instance decision (in days)
Durable Solutions	General	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do refugees receive preferential treatment in naturalization procedures? • Do stateless persons receive preferential treatment in naturalization procedures? • Does the government permit the local integration of refugees? • Is any undue pressure exercised on refugees influencing their voluntary choice to repatriate? • Does the government allow access to land / agricultural production to refugees / asylum-seekers? • Does the government allow access to land / agricultural production to refugees / asylum-seekers?

Source: UNHCR Guidelines on Temporary protection 2014: Standards and Indicators in UNHCR Operations, available at <http://www.unhcr.org/40eaa9804.pdf>, p. 63.

ANNEX V: MICRO LEVEL INTERVIEWEES

Table 2: Micro-level Interviewees

Code	Nationality	Age	Legal Status	Interview	Notes	Gender
INF01	Iranian	35-44	Refugee	Glasgow		Female
INM01	Iranian	40-49	Refugee	Glasgow		Male
INM02	Iranian	44-54	Refugee	Glasgow		Male
IQM01	Iraqi	35-44	Refugee	Glasgow		Male
PKM01	Pakistani	25-34	Asylum Seeker (Unregistered, homeless)	Glasgow		Male
PKM02	Pakistani	35-44	Asylum Seeker (Case withdrawn, seeking citizenship via British wife)	Glasgow		Male

SYM01	Syrian	Unknown	Refugee	Glasgow		Male
AFM01	Afghan	25-34	Asylum seeker	Glasgow		Male
SYF01	Syrian	Unknown	Refugee	Glasgow		Female
SYM02	Syrian	25-34	Refugee	Glasgow		Male
IQF01	Iraqi	25-34	Asylum seeker	Cambridge	Yazidi	Female
SYM03	Syrian	25-34	Refugee	Cambridge	Assyrian	Male
IQM02	Iraqi	25-34	Asylum seeker (rejected, homeless)	Cambridge	Yazidi	Male
SYM04	Syrian	25-34	Refugee	Cambridge	Assyrian	Male
IQM03	Iraqi	35-44	Asylum seeker (refused, fresh claim)	Cambridge	Yazidi	Male

ANNEX VI: MESO LEVEL INTERVIEW PARTNERS

Asylum Seeker Housing Project (ASH)

Asylum Welcome group

Former Employee of the Red Cross

Govan Community Project worker

Just Right Scotland

Maryhill Integration Network

NHS Scotland

Police Scotland

Scottish Green Party councillor

Syrian Sisters group

Other organisations participated anonymously.